

Spectrophotometric and FT-IR studies of interaction of narcotic drugs (morphine, codeine and thebaine) with acceptors (HQ, BQ, NQ, PA, *o*-Chlo, DNB), their thermodynamics and determination of the vertical ionization potentials of the drugs[†]

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Abstract : Morphine, codeine and thebaine formed charge transfer complexes with acceptors like hydroquinone, benzoquinone, naphthaquinone, picric acid, chloranil and dinitrobenzene as evidenced from the shifting of absorption maxima and change in optical densities in the UV regions. The evidence of complex formation was observed from the optical densities of the complex in the visible region when $D \gg A$ and where D and A do not absorb. The evidence of complex formation was also adduced from FT-IR measurements for morphine + naphthaquinone, codeine + naphthaquinone and thebaine + naphthaquinone complexes. The formations of CT complexes with those acceptors are confirmed from the plots of $h\nu_{CT}$ against I_D^V (vertical ionization potential) of the drugs. From the values CT transition energies, the vertical ionization potentials (I_D^V) of morphine, codeine and thebaine were estimated to be 7.228 ± 0.396 , 7.236 ± 0.399 and 7.233 ± 0.405 eV respectively. The almost equal values are due to structural similarities of the drugs. The degrees of overlap in the ground state of the complexes were also calculated. The association constants and thermodynamics of the complexes (e.g. ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0) were determined spectrophotometrically from the o.d measurements at 298, 303, 306 and 310 K using D and A in stoichiometric ratios, a condition necessary for the accurate determination of the association constants. The complexes are fairly stable.

Keywords : Complex, degree of charge transfer, drugs, FT-IR, spectrophotometry, thermodynamics, vertical ionization potential.

Introduction

Morphine, codeine and thebaine are the main constituents of opium and are structurally related narcotic analgesics obtainable from plant source (Poppy plant, *Papaver somniferum*)^{1,2} having concentration ranges between 4 to 21% for morphine, 0.7 to 3% for codeine and 0.2 to 1% for thebaine. Morphine and related compounds act principally on the Central Nervous System (CNS) causing analgesia, drowsiness, change in mood, respiratory depression, nausea, vomiting, decreased gastrointestinal motility and alterations of the endocrine and autonomic nervous systems^{3,4}.

In view of the addictive properties of the opium alkaloids, these substances are of great importance in forensic science. Morphine, codeine and related compounds [diacetyl morphine (Heroin), 6-acetylmorphine, acetyl

codeine etc.] are important illicit drugs and widely abused internationally^{3,4}.

Morphine, due to its peculiar structure (Fig. 1)¹ has been subjected to various structural modifications to give compounds of varied analgesic and other medicinal activities^{1,2,5}. The relationship between chemical structure and analgesic action and some aspects like drug-receptor interactions were widely studied^{1,2,6,7-9}. Drug action, in molecular terms, can be regarded to be the ultimate consequences of physico-chemical interactions of the drug with some natural receptor molecules where

(i) drugs may compete with the natural substance for the active or allosteric site of an enzyme inhibiting enzymic activities.

(ii) drugs may react with an essential metabolite in-

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. Aditya on his 85th birthday.

Fig. 1¹. (a) Structure of morphine, (b) structure of codeine, (c) structure of thebaine and (d) diagram of the surface of the analgesic receptor site with the corresponding lower surface of the drug molecule (morphine).

intermediate or with some natural macromolecules such as a structural cytoplasmic or enzyme protein, a nucleic acid or lipopolysaccharide^{1,2}.

However, the first step is the association of drug with receptor molecule. In general, the drugs are usually held to the receptors reversibly by ionic or weak bonds so that the drug leaves the receptor site when the concentration of drug decreases in the extra cellular fluids.

Stabilization of the complexes may be due to ionic, covalent and co-ordinate covalent bonding. However in general a combination of weak physico-chemical forces like hydrogen-bonding, charge-transfer interactions, hydrophobic interactions, van der Waals forces etc. are involved in the stabilization of drug receptor complex of

which a particular type of interaction or bond formation usually has a decisive impact.

Charge transfer complexes are useful as potential high efficiency second order non-linear optical (NLO) materials¹⁰, as semiconductors¹¹⁻¹⁴ and as catalysts¹¹. The formation of EDA complexes with medicines and bio-molecules are well known^{15,16}.

Studies on charge transfer interactions are useful for understanding the forces responsible for ion solvent interactions¹⁷⁻²¹. Recently, vertical ionization potentials of drugs and a number of crown ethers were determined from charge transfer bands of EDA complexes²²⁻²⁴. Charge transfer bands of EDA complexes of TNT with different amines were also studied by FT-IR method²⁵.

These consideration led us to study the weak interactions namely charge transfer and hydrogen-bond formation, van der Waals interactions etc. between morphine and related drugs with a number of acceptors like hydroquinone (HQ), *p*-benzoquinone (BQ), 1,4-naphthaquinone (NQ), picric acid (PA), *o*-chloranil (*o*-Chlo), 1,2-dinitrobenzene (DNB) spectrophotometrically. Attempts were made to determine the vertical ionization potentials of morphine, codeine and thebaine from CT bands of these complexes with known acceptors. The association constants of the complexes and their thermodynamics were studied using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Evidence for complex formation was studied using FT-IR measurements.

The results of our investigations are presented in this communication.

Material and methods :

Purification of drugs - morphine (Opium Factory, Gazipur, UP) was dissolved in methanol and crystallized twice. Codeine (Opium Factory, Gazipur, UP) was dissolved in ethanol and crystallized twice. Thebaine (Opium Factory, Gazipur, UP) was purified by sublimation in a steam bath. Hydroquinone (G.R., E. Merck) was taken as such. Benzoquinone (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by sublimation in a steam bath till bright yellow crystals were obtained. Naphthaquinone (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallization from dry ethanol. *o*-Chloranil (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallization from dry ether and followed by sublimation. 1,2-Dinitrobenzene (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallization from dry ethanol. Picric acid (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallization from boiling water.

Purity of the samples was checked by melting point determination.

Methanol (Spectroscopic grade, E. Merck) was used as such.

All other chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade from E. Merck.

Spectroscopic measurements were taken with a Shimadzu Double Beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer model UV 2550 (2001) with thermoelectrically temperature controlled bath with an accuracy of ± 0.1 °C. Morphine, codeine, thebaine absorb strongly in the UV region. The ligands like HQ, BQ, NQ, PA, DNB, *o*-chloranil

also absorb strongly in the UV region. The alkaloids when mixed with each of the ligand showed shift in the absorption maxima and change in optical densities indicating complex formation. The wavelengths of absorption maxima are recorded in Tables 1-3. Typical absorption curves are presented in Figs. 2 and 3.

No solvent shift phenomenon was observed for drugs using solvents like methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile, benzene, heptane and carbon tetrachloride indicating no solute-solvent interactions.

Determination of association constants spectrophotometrically :

For the determination of association constants of the complexes drug (D) (like morphine, codeine and thebaine), was mixed with acceptors mentioned above in stoichiometric ratios and the absorption measurements were made at different temperatures at the wavelengths of complex formation.

To identify charge transfer (CT) bands more accurately, the spectra containing a definite concentration of drug ($\sim 10^{-5}$ M) mixed with different but large concentrations of acceptor (A) ($\sim 10^{-2}$ M) with varying strength, were measured in the visible range (350-900 nm). There was no conspicuous absorption maxima, but the complexes were found to absorb in the visible regions where D or A showed no absorption (Figs. 4a and 4b).

FT-IR measurements :

For the measurement of Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectra, D and A in methanol were mixed in equimolecular proportions and the solutions were evaporated to dryness. Experiment was performed only in case of naphthaquinone complexes. The dried crystalline products were used for FT-IR measurements. The FT-IR spectra of morphine, codeine, thebaine, naphthaquinone and the complexes were recorded using Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model "Spectrum GX FT-IR" in KBr disk (Figs. 5-8) with a resolution 4.00 cm^{-1} . IR spectra were recorded over the range 700 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . The standard temperature for measurements was 298 K.

Results

Assuming 1 : 1 complex formation between the drugs (D) acting as donors and the ligands (A) acting as acceptors, the equilibrium constant for the reaction,

Table 1. λ_{\max} , equilibrium constant (K), extinction coefficient (ϵ) and free energy (ΔG^0), enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) values for complexes between morphine and different acceptors at different temperatures in methanol

Name of drug	λ_{\max} of drug (nm)	λ_{\max} of acceptors (nm)	λ_{\max} of complexes (nm)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 25 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 29 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 33 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 37 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	ϵ ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH^0 (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^0 (J/mol/deg)
Morphine	286	294, 226	290	0.64	0.70	0.72	0.73	4527	27.4	8.16	119.4
		290.5, 243	241	20.52	15.6	11.6	-	12386	36.01	-54.0	-60.36
		331.5, 246.5	333, 240	11.94	10.85	8.23	-	23039	34.67	-23.54	37.31
		352, 293	355, 288	8.44	8.1	7.7	7.2	20531	33.81	-10.1	79.54
<i>o</i> -Chlo		268.5	262	8.59	8.4	8.2	8.0	12922	33.85	-4.55	98.3
DNB				10.7	10.1	9.69	9.2	9391	34.4	-9.39	83.88

HQ = Hydroquinone, BQ = benzoquinone, NQ = naphthaquinone, PA = picric acid, *o*-Chlo = *o*-chlorani, DNB = 1,2-dinitrobenzene.

Table 2. λ_{\max} , equilibrium constant (K), extinction coefficient (ϵ) and free energy (ΔG^0), enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) values for complexes between codeine and different acceptors at different temperatures in methanol.

Name of drug	λ_{\max} of drug (nm)	λ_{\max} of acceptors (nm)	λ_{\max} of complexes (nm)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 25 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 29 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 33 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 37 °C ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	ϵ ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH^0 (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^0 (J/mol/deg)
Codeine	286	294, 226	289	0.40	0.34	0.25	0.16	4793	26.2	-44.38	-60.67
		290.5, 243	240	8.0	8.81	9.16	-	12293	33.7	12.66	155.5
		331.5, 246.5	333, 240	2.43	2.6	2.7	2.9	24798	30.7	12.24	144.1
		352, 293	355, 289, 247	8.74	7.83	6.91	6.01	16335	33.9	-34.88	-3.29
<i>o</i> -Chlo		268.5	262	7.59	7.41	7.25	7.1	12866	33.55	-4.26	98.26
DNB				23.2	21.2	19.1	15.7	12074	36.3	-24.43	39.86

HQ = Hydroquinone, BQ = benzoquinone, NQ = naphthaquinone, PA = picric acid, *o*-Chlo = *o*-chlorani, DNB = 1,2-dinitrobenzene.

Table 3. λ_{max} , equilibrium constant (K), extinction coefficient (ϵ) and free energy (ΔG^\ominus), enthalpy (ΔH^\ominus) and entropy (ΔS^\ominus) values for complexes between thebaine and different acceptors at different temperatures in methanol

Name of drug	λ_{max} of drug (nm)	λ_{max} of acceptors (nm)	λ_{max} of complexes (nm)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 25 °C ($dm^2 mol^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 29 °C ($dm^2 mol^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 33 °C ($dm^2 mol^{-1}$)	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-5}$ at 37 °C ($dm^2 mol^{-1}$)	ϵ ($dm^2 mol^{-1}$)	$-\Delta G^\ominus$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ominus (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ominus (J/mol/deg)
Thebaine	285.5	HQ 294, 226	288.5	0.160	0.168	0.186	0.193	13293	23.98	12.75	123.27
		BQ 290.5, 243	234, 284	0.147	0.139	0.136	0.130	28069	23.8	-7.84	53.45
		NQ 331.5, 246.5	332.5, 240	6.82	6.54	5.68	4.82	30631	33.28	-56.12	-76.66
		PA 352	355	0.73	0.54	0.40	=	17611	27.74	-56.98	-98.12
		<i>o</i> -Chlo 293	290	8.26	7.7	7.5	7.0	11640	33.76	-10.03	79.59
		DNB 268.5	270	0.56	0.54	0.51	0.50	9490	27.09	-7.6	65.4

HQ = Hydroquinone, BQ = benzoquinone, NQ = naphthaquinone, PA = picric acid, *o*-Chlo = *o*-chloranil, DNB = 1,2-dinitrobenzene.

Table 4. Free energy (ΔG^\ominus), enthalpy (ΔH^\ominus), entropy (ΔS^\ominus) and C_p values for complexes between morphine, codeine and thebaine with different receptors using relations 4-7

	Morphine				Codeine				Thebaine			
	$-\Delta G^\ominus$ (kJ/mol)	ΔH^\ominus (kJ/mol)	ΔS^\ominus (J/mol/deg)	C_p	$-\Delta G^\ominus$ (kJ/mol)	ΔH^\ominus (kJ/mol)	ΔS^\ominus (J/mol/deg)	C_p	$-\Delta G^\ominus$ (kJ/mol)	ΔH^\ominus (kJ/mol)	ΔS^\ominus (J/mol/deg)	C_p
HQ	27.42	8.01 (8.16)	119.42 (119.42)	-1.714	26.258	-45.18 (-44.38)	-62.74 (-60.67)	-7.209	23.98	12.49 (12.75)	122.34 (123.27)	-0.2857
BQ	36.01	-53.5 (-54.0)	-60.99 (-60.36)	-1.6	33.682	13.31 (12.66)	155.26 (155.6)	-2.641	23.778	-7.8 (-7.84)	54.25 (53.45)	0.2095
NQ	34.67	-23.42 (-23.54)	37.42 (37.31)	-1.714	30.729	12.283 (12.24)	144.37 (144.2)	0.171	33.287	-22.50 (-22.66)	35.58 (35.65)	-11.123
PA	33.814	-10.4 (-10.1)	80.52 (79.54)	-0.704	33.901	-23.50 (-23.956)	32.92 (33.37)	-2.4	27.749	-56.42 (-56.98)	-98.39 (-98.12)	-0.32
<i>o</i> -Chlo	33.858	-4.03 (-4.55)	100.07 (98.3)	-0.0857	33.551	-4.576 (-4.26)	97.23 (98.26)	0.0476	33.761	-9.98 (-10.03)	79.16 (79.59)	-0.0476
DNB	34.398	-10.53 (-9.39)	80.09 (83.88)	0.0285	36.32	-24.0 (-24.43)	39.3 (39.86)	-2.714	27.092	-7.56 (-7.6)	65.54 (65.4)	0.3619

Values in parenthesis are obtained using eq. (4).

Fig. 2. Overlay absorption spectrum of morphine, codeine and thebaine.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectrum of (a) codeine, (b) picric acid and (c) complex of codeine + picric acid.

can be written as

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \cdot \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \cdot \gamma_A} = \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \quad (2)$$

In view of non-electrolytic nature of the reactants and complexes and at low concentrations $\gamma_{DA}/\gamma_D \cdot \gamma_A$ (γ represents activity coefficients of the respective species)

can be regarded to be unity. C_1 and C_2 represents the initial concentrations of D and A respectively, x represent the equilibrium concentration of the complex DA.

The reactants were mixed in equimolar proportions and the reactants and the complex absorbed in the same region, thus the usual procedure of determining K_{DA} using Benesi-Hildebrand²⁶, or Scott²⁷, equation were avoided

Fig. 4a. Variation of CT absorption spectra of morphine and benzoquinone complexes at different concentrations.

Fig. 4b. Variation of CT absorption spectra of morphine and naphthaquinone complexes at different concentrations.

and an iterative^{17-21,28,29} procedure using the equation,

$$\frac{C_1}{(d - d_1 - d_2)} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)(C_2 - x)l} \cdot \frac{1}{K_{DA}} \quad (\text{where } l = 1 \text{ cm}) \quad (3)$$

was used for the determination of association constants.

$$\text{Here, } d_1 = \epsilon_1 C_1 l$$

$$d_2 = \epsilon_2 C_2 l$$

$$d = \epsilon x l + \epsilon_1 (C_1 - x) l + \epsilon_2 (C_2 - x) l$$

$$x = \frac{d - d_1 - d_2}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)l}$$

Fig. 5. FT-IR spectra of morphine, codeine and thebaine.

Fig. 6. FT-IR spectra of morphine and subtraction spectra of morphine + NQ - NQ-morphine.

x was assumed to be zero initially, and from the plot of $C_1/(d - d_1 - d_2)$ against $1/C_2$, an approximate values of $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ and x were determined.

The value of x was utilized to get a refined value of x

from the plot of $C_1/(d - d_1 - d_2)$ against $1/(C_2 - x)$. The iteration was repeated till constant values of $1/(\epsilon - \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ and K_{DA} were obtained.

The molar absorptivities ϵ of the complexes and the

Fig. 7. FT-IR spectra of codeine and subtraction spectra of codeine + NQ – NQ-codeine.

Fig. 8. FT-IR spectra of thebaine and subtraction spectra of thebaine + NQ – NQ-thebaine.

equilibrium constants K_{DA} at different temperatures (298, 302, 306 and 310 K) are recorded in Tables 1–3.

The constancy and consistency in the ϵ and K_{DA} values show that the composition of the complexes was 1 : 1.

ΔH^0 values of the complexes were determined from the plot $\log K_{DA}$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 9) assuming C_p values to be constant in the temperature ranges (298–310 K). ΔG^0 and ΔS^0 for the reactions were calculated using the relations,

Fig. 9. Plot of $\log K$ against T^{-1} for a series of (a) morphine, (b) codeine and (c) thebaine + donors (HQ, BQ, NQ, PA, *o*-Chlo, DNB) complexes

$$\Delta G^0 = -2.303 RT \log K_{DA} = \Delta H^0 - T\Delta S^0 \quad (4)$$

ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values of the complexes are given in Tables 1-3.

ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values were also calculated using the relations,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^0 &= -2.303 RT \log K_{DA} \\ &= a + bT + c T \log T \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta H^0 = a - cT \quad (6)$$

and

$$\Delta S^0 = -b - c - (c \times \log T) \quad (7)$$

The data and the values of a , b , c are presented in Tables 4 and 5. The values of C_p are negligible in most of the cases in the temperature range studied.

Discussion

Morphine, codeine and thebaine are structurally similar (Fig. 1) and have phenanthrene type of structure. The analgesic properties of codeine is 15 and thebaine (most toxic) is zero w.r.t morphine as 100¹.

The unique analgesic morphine was subjected to various modifications to find suitable potent analgesic without addictive properties. Unfortunately, increase in analgesic activity was observed to be associated with increase in addictive properties.

Due to peculiar structure, morphine and related compounds can interact with compounds of variable structures and the interactions^{1,2,5-7} are also variable.

According to Snyder³⁰, "morphine and most opiates have a rigid T-shaped structure with two broad water repelling surfaces at right angles to each other, a hydroxyl group (OH) capable of hydrogen bonding and a positively charged nitrogen atom that can form an ionic bond, all suggesting possible non-covalent interactions with a geometrically and complementary receptor site".

The three essential sites of receptor topography for morphine type analgesic are [Fig. 1(d)] :

- (i) A flat structure that allows a linkage with the aromatic ring of the drug through van der Waals type forces.
- (ii) An anionic site able to associate with the positively charged basic centers of the drugs.
- (iii) A suitably oriented cavity in order to accommodate the $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$ portion (relative to carbons 15 to 16) projecting from the piperidine that lies in front of the plane containing the aromatic ring and the basic center.

Portoghese³¹, postulated formation of different complexes of narcotic analgesics with receptors. More than one type of D-R complexation with different modes of interactions are possible^{1,2,8} though D-R interactions are not properly understood. Using X-ray diffraction data, Jung and Landi³², calculated the distances between the active groups of morphine and codeine and the results indicate a receptor to be of elastic dimension and there can be more than one kind of analgesic receptor.

However, conformational changes have been shown to have no effect on analgesic property i.e stereo specificity is not important^{1,2,8}.

The purpose of the present investigation is not to throw

Table 5. Calculation of constants of *a*, *b* and *c* using equation $\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K = a + bT + c 2.303 T \log T$ for morphine, codeine and thebaine with different receptors

	Morphine			Codeine			Thebaine		
	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>
HQ	518.79	-11.60	1.714	2103.1	-48.224	7.209	97.638	-2.036	0.2857
BQ	423.3	-10.65	1.6	800.328	-17.845	2.641	-70.231	1.349	-0.2095
NQ	487.35	-11.52	1.714	-38.675	1.001	-0.171	894.148	-20.639	3.076
PA	199.39	-4.79	0.704	143.94	-3.796	0.562	38.94	-2.045	0.32
<i>o</i> -Chlo	21.50	-0.67	0.0857	-18.761	0.221	-0.0476	4.204	-0.398	0.0476
DNB	-19.02	0.11	-0.0285	784.772	-18.218	2.714	-115.405	2.3585	-0.3619

$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K = a + bT + c 2.303 T \log T$
 $\Delta H = a - cT$
 $\Delta S = -b - c - (c \times 2.303 \log T)$
 $C_p = -c$

light on drug-receptor interactions but to explore the forces responsible for D-R interactions and their biologic effects.

From the structure of the morphine and related compounds, it is apparent that interactions of these drugs with different acceptors or molecules are possible. The reactions will be different for different acceptors and the facts are also validated from the present study.

All the drugs absorb in the UV region and the absorption spectra is given in Figs. 2 and 3. The absorption peaks (nm) are given in table below :

	$\sigma - \sigma^*$	$\pi - \pi^*$	$n - \pi^*$
Morphine	210.8	240	286
Codeine	212.2	244	286
Thebaine	206.0	227	285.5

The values near 210 nm must be due to $\sigma - \sigma^*$ transitions. The cut off value for methanol solvent is 210 nm and the spectra were not measured in N_2 atmosphere. Thus, inspite of baseline corrections, there may be uncertainty in values below 220 nm. The absorption maxima due to $n - \pi^*$ transitions in the long wavelength region almost remain the same but a gradual blue shift is observed with the gradual substitution of phenolic and alcoholic -OH groups by -OCH₃ group. But in case of $\pi - \pi^*$ transitions (as well as for $\sigma - \sigma^*$ transitions), red shift was observed when phenolic -OH group is methylated as in codeine but blue shift is observed when both -OH groups are methylated as in thebaine. The strong absorption and the considerable blue shift in thebaine may be due to additional $\pi - \pi^*$ bond where H-bonding should be greatly reduced.

The maxima of the acceptors [HQ, BQ, NQ, PA, DNB, *o*-chloranil] are given in Tables 1-3 and obviously arise

due to $\pi - \pi^*$ and $n - \pi^*$ transitions.

There are visible changes in the spectra when the drugs (morphine *etc.*) were mixed with the acceptors, though there were slight shifts in absorption maxima but there were profound changes in optical densities (Tables 1-3 and Fig. 3) indicating complex formation. Unfortunately the components and the complexes absorb in the same region. In general, there were both red and blue shifts with respect to drugs and usually blue shift is observed with respect to acceptors with exceptions. However, the absorptions of the solutions containing $D \approx 10^{-5}$ (M) and [A] variable but in large excess (10^{-3} M) showed no conspicuous peaks though absorptions of the mixtures were fairly high indicating definite complex formation (Figs. 4a and 4b) as both D and A have no absorption in this region.

In order to get better insight regarding the complexes, FT-IR experiments were performed in few cases in the solid state though the behavior in the solid state and in solutions differs considerably. Principal FT-IR peaks of morphine, codeine and thebaine recorded in Table 6 show that the peaks determined by us using KBr disc ($700-4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) agree with the limited values given by Moffat ($650-2000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)³³. Slight changes were noted and the additional values were also observed. FT-IR spectra of the complexes of NQ with morphine, codeine and thebaine and their residual uncomplexed components were also measured. The frequency changes due to complex formation were examined by computer subtracting of IR spectra of the components like morphine (M) or codeine (C) or thebaine (T) and naphthaquinone (NQ) from the respective complexes along with their components like [M + NQ] - [NQ] - [M] (Figs. 5-8). Some additional

peaks and shift in IR frequencies were noted. But these are of secondary importance.

Charge transfer complex formation and determination of vertical ionization potentials of drugs :

The possibility of CT complex formation between morphine, codeine and thebaine with acceptors like hydroquinone, benzoquinone, naphthaquinone, *o*-chloranil, 1,2-dinitrobenzene, picric acid was examined from the plots of $h\nu_{CT}$ (transition energy) of the complexes of different acceptors or donors against I_D (ionization constant obtained from AM1 method) or E_A (electron affinity) as the case may be using the McConnell-Ham-Platt equation³⁴,

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_D - E_A - w \quad (8)$$

E_A = electron affinity of the acceptor and w is the dissociation energy of the charge transfer in the excited state.

The extent of charge transfer in the ground state and determination of experimental vertical ionization potential (I_D^V) of morphine, codeine and thebaine were made following the theoretical equation suggested by Mulliken³⁵.

The equation is

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_D^V - C_1 + \frac{C_2}{I_D^V - C_1} \quad (9)$$

where $C_1 = E_A^V + G_1 + G_0$ (10)

G_0 is the binding energy of no-bond function where the binding results from physical forces like dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole interactions, London dispersion forces and hydrogen bonding, whereas G_1 is related to the energy of the 'dative' structure of the complex corresponding to the complete transfer of one electron from donor to the acceptor. G_1 arises mainly from the electrostatic energy of attraction between D^+ and A^- . The term C_2 is related to the resonance energy of interaction between the 'no-bond' and dative forms in the ground and excited states and assumed to be constant for a given acceptor.

The eq. (10) can be rearranged as follows

$$2C_1 + h\nu_{CT} = \frac{C_1(C_1 + h\nu_{CT})}{I_D^V} + \frac{C_2}{I_D^V} + I_D^V \quad (11)$$

The vertical electron affinities are taken from the AM1. G_0 term is neglected and G_1 is taken to be 4.13 (eV) as utilized by Saha and Mukherjee, Bhattacharyya *et al.*²²⁻²⁴ from the relation $e^2/4\pi\epsilon_0 r$ or taking the typical D-A distance to be 3.5 Å.

The values C_1 is obtained for each receptor using the eq. (11). A plot of $2C_1 + h\nu_{CT}$ against $C_1 (C_1 + h\nu_{CT})$ for a given donor and various acceptors gave a slope of $1/I_D^V$ from which the value of I_D^V of the donor can be obtained (Fig. 10).

(a) morphine

(b) codeine

(c) thebaine

Fig. 10. Plot of $2C_1 + h\nu_{CT}$ vs $C_1(C_1 + h\nu_{CT})$ for a series of (a) morphine, (b) codeine and (c) thebaine + donors (HQ, BQ, NQ, PA, *o*-Chlo, DNB) complexes.

The following linear regression equations have been obtained with the present data.

Morphine :

$$2C_1 + hv_{CT} = (0.13834 \pm 0.00757)[C_1(C_1 + hv_{CT})] + 7.741 \pm 0.4644; \text{ correlation coefficient} = 0.994, s.d = 0.24$$

Codeine :

$$2C_1 + hv_{CT} = (0.1382 \pm 0.0076)[C_1(C_1 + hv_{CT})] + 7.75126 \pm 0.46626; \text{ correlation coefficient} = 0.994, s.d = 0.24$$

Thebaine :

$$2C_1 + hv_{CT} = (0.13825 \pm 0.00772)[C_1(C_1 + hv_{CT})] + 7.74901 \pm 0.47374; \text{ correlation coefficient} = 0.9938, s.d = 0.244$$

Tables 7-10 show the experimental transition energies. The plots were found to be linear. From the plots, I_D^V for morphine, codeine and thebaine were found as 7.228 ± 0.396 , 7.2358 ± 0.399 and 7.233 ± 0.405 eV respectively. The experimental I_D^V values of morphine, codeine and thebaine obtained in this way differ with the theoretical values (AM1).

Degree of charge transfer :

Using the Mulliken model³⁵, the ground state (ψ_G) and excited state (ψ_E) wave functions of the CT complexes are a linear combination of dative $\psi(D^0, A^0)$ and ionic $\psi(D^+, A^-)$ states (where transfer of an electron from donor to acceptor takes place),

$$\psi_G = \sqrt{1 - \alpha}\psi(D^0, A^0) + \sqrt{\alpha}\psi(D^+, A^-) \quad (12)$$

$$\psi_E = \sqrt{1 - \alpha}\psi(D^+, A^-) - \sqrt{\alpha}\psi(D^0, A^0) \quad (13)$$

where α is the degree of charge transfer.

α is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{C_2}{2(I_D^V - E_A + C_1)^2 + C_2} \quad (14)$$

C_2 is obtained from the intercept which is equal to

$$\left(\frac{C_2}{I_D^V} + I_D^V \right) \text{ of the eq. (11).}$$

α values of morphine, codeine and thebaine complexes were found to be nearly 1.416×10^{-2} , 1.423×10^{-2} and

Table 6. FT-IR data of complexes

	Morphine	Codeine	Thebaine
Principal IR peaks (cm ⁻¹) in KBr disk ³³	1243, 1118, 1086, 945, 833, 805	1500, 1268, 1111, 1052, 934, 793	1605, 1234, 1270, 1144, 1030, 910
FT-IR peaks (cm ⁻¹) obtained in the drugs using KBr disk	3208, 2938, (2916), 2858, 2822, 2361, 1635, 1604, 1445, 1368, 1328, 1307, 1247, 1197, 1142, 1119, 1087, 1027, 978, 961, 943, 885, 833, 802, 759, (719), 707, 674	3533, 3020, 2962, 2928, 2833, 2788, 2763, 1636, 1603, 1501, 1454, 1385, 1327, 1275, 1249, 1200, 1184, 1057, 936, 796	(3002), (2963), 2929, (2909), 2836, 2794, 2360, (1667), (1629), (1465), (1371), (1322)
Additional FT-IR peaks (cm ⁻¹) obtained in complex with NQ using KBr disk ^a	1636, 1677, 654	2360, 1586, 864	2341, 1653, 1540, 1377, 1329, 1300, 1114, 1100, 957, 936

^aValues taken subtracting spectra of respective drugs, NQ from complex.

Values in parenthesis are absence in complex.

Table 7. Wavelengths at CT absorption maxima and transition energies ($h\nu_{CT}$) of morphine + different acceptors complexes and HOMO energies of the acceptors

Acceptors	λ_{max} (nm)	$h\nu_{CT}$ (eV)	HOMO energy (eV) (AM1)	LUMO energy (eV) (AM1)	$2C_1 +$ $h\nu_{CT}$	$C_1(C_1 +$ $h\nu_{CT})$
HQ	290	4.256	8.734	-0.233	12.05	31.77224
BQ	241.5	5.111	10.876	1.735	16.841	64.37424
NQ	240	5.143	10.256	1.546	16.495	61.40864
PA	355	3.477	11.414	2.534	16.805	67.57962
<i>o</i> -Chlo	289	4.271	10.100	2.410	17.351	70.70394
DNB	262	4.711	11.338	1.843	16.657	63.81553

Table 8. Wavelengths at CT absorption maxima and transition energies ($h\nu_{CT}$) of codeine + different acceptors complexes and HOMO energies of the acceptors

Acceptors	λ_{max} (nm)	$h\nu_{CT}$ (eV)	$2C_1 + h\nu_{CT}$	$C_1(C_1 + h\nu_{CT})$
HQ	289	4.271	12.065	31.8307
BQ	240	5.143	16.873	64.5619
NQ	240	5.143	16.495	61.4086
PA	355	3.477	16.805	67.5796
<i>o</i> -Chlo	289	4.271	17.351	70.7039
DNB	262	4.711	16.657	63.8155

Table 9. Wavelengths at CT absorption maxima and transition energies ($h\nu_{CT}$) of thebaine + different acceptors complexes and HOMO energies of the acceptors

Acceptors	λ_{max} (nm)	$h\nu_{CT}$ (eV)	$2C_1 + h\nu_{CT}$	$C_1(C_1 + h\nu_{CT})$
HQ	288.5	4.279	12.073	31.86187
BQ	234	5.275	17.005	65.3361
NQ	240	5.143	16.495	61.4086
PA	355	3.477	16.805	67.57962
<i>o</i> -Chlo	290	4.256	17.336	70.60584
DNB	269	4.589	16.535	63.08683

Table 10. Theoretical (AM1) and experimentally determined I_D values of morphine, codeine and thebaine

Donor	I_D (eV)	
	AM1	Expt.
Morphine	8.461	7.2285 ± 0.396
Codeine	8.442	7.2358 ± 0.399
Thebaine	8.384	7.2332 ± 0.405

1.424×10^{-2} respectively. Low α value indicates little charge transfer in the ground state.

Formation constants and the thermodynamics of complexes :

The association constants of the complexes were measured using D and A in stoichiometric ratios. All the acceptors form fairly stable complexes with the morphine, codeine and thebaine as observed from high values of the association constants K_{DA} where the reported values of K_{DA} given in the literature^{4,9} are low for charge transfer or hydrogen bonded complexes. K_{DA} values of charge transfer and hydrogen bonded complexes are determined spectrophotometrically using Benesi-Hildebrand equation²⁵ where A and D are usually of the order 10^{-4} - 10^{-5} M and $D \gg A$ ($\approx 10^{-2}$ M) and in the calculation [DA] is neglected as $[D] \gg \gg [DA]$.

Thus, we have

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[(A) - (DA)][D]}$$

Low values of K_{DA} are expected and will be considerably different from K_{DA} values when [A], [D] and [DA] are of the same order of magnitude (10^{-4} - 10^{-5} M) as

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[(A) - (DA)][(D) - (DA)]}$$

Naturally, K_{DA} will be high.

The high K_{DA} values suggest fairly strong complex formation. The critical analysis of Foster³⁶ show that the results obtained by using $D \gg A$ are erroneous and the accurate values are obtained only when the concentrations of [A] and [D] are comparable.

The structures of drugs suggest that combinations of forces are probably responsible for the formation of complexes but the forces are obviously different and dependent on the nature of the substance. It is apparent that irreversible covalent complex formation is not possible and they form reversible complexes and weak forces like charge transfer interactions, hydrogen-bonding, hydrophobic interactions, van der Waals interactions etc. are responsible for complex formations.

All the reactants form stable complexes with the drugs but the order of stabilities are different in spite of their structural similarities.

The stability of the complexes as observed from $-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol⁻¹) are

For morphine : BQ > NQ > DNB > *o*-Chlo >
PA > HQ

For codeine : DNB > PA > BQ > *o*-Chlo > NQ
> HQ

For thebaine : *o*-Chlo > NQ > PA > DNB > HQ
> BQ

The enthalpy changes (ΔH^0) and entropy changes (ΔS^0) are in the order of increasing values (from exothermic to endothermic)

Morphine ΔH^0 : BQ < NQ < PA < DNB
< *o*-Chlo < HQ

ΔS^0 : BQ < NQ < PA < DNB
< *o*-Chlo < HQ

Codeine ΔH^0 : HQ < PA < DNB < *o*-Chlo
< NQ < BQ

ΔS^0 : HQ < PA < DNB < *o*-Chlo
< NQ < BQ

Thebaine ΔH^0 : PA < NQ < *o*-Chlo < BQ
< DNB < HQ

ΔS^0 : PA < NQ < BQ < DNB
< *o*-Chlo < HQ

All the reactants have planar benzene ring modified by the substituents. Planarity is disturbed in case of HQ, PA and 1,2-DNB. Here shape and size of the molecules are important to have a good fit in the cavity of drug molecules. N-atom may be involved in hydrogen bond formation with -OH group or bridged atom but slightly buckled structure may be responsible for van der Waals bond formation with HQ and PA where dispersion forces are strong due to presence of OH and NO₂ group.

Charge transfer and van der Waals interactions arising from dispersion effects and planarity of the molecules are responsible for complex formation of the drug with *o*-chloranil and 1,2-dinitrobenzene. Hydrogen bond formation may not be important due to positional disadvantages. But the drug molecules have variable dipole moment and dipole-dipole interactions and dipole-induced dipole interaction play very important role. Furthermore, drug may interact with hydrophobic CH₃ groups and hydrophilic OH groups leading to the distortion of the hydrogen bonded chain structure of the solvent methanol.

The stability of the complexes is the result of the combination of all these factors. ΔG^0 results from the compensation of ΔH^0 and $T\Delta S^0$. The entropy factor rather than the strength of the bonds appears to be the deciding though the strength of the H-bonds (greatest in morphine and least in thebaine) may be important. The entropy changes arise from two factors ΔS^0_{int} and ΔS^0_{ext} . ΔS^0_{int} is the entropy change which arises from the structural changes in D-A molecules and strains and stresses involved to accommodate the receptors in the space near the piperidine moiety. ΔS^0_{ext} is the entropy change, which arises from the solvational changes occurring in the system due to complex formation. Both ΔS^0_{int} and ΔS^0_{ext} are expected to change from morphine to thebaine.

It is to be noted that though ΔG^0 values of a large number of CT complexes are known but ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values are of very limited. Moreover, most of the ΔG^0 values derived using Benesi-Hildebrand equation where taking D >> A are erroneous. Few data of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 are available for simple systems, but the large values of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 cannot be accounted for.

Due to the peculiarities of the structures of morphine, codeine and thebaine, there are possibility of hydrogen bonding capabilities of variable magnitude of the drugs and probable accommodation of different groups into their structural moieties. It is rational to believe that a combination of CT interactions, H-bonding and van der Waals interactions of variable magnitude are responsible for the changes in entropy and enthalpy values leading to complex formation. The values are different depending on the nature of the donor groups. HQ and PA may have greater H-bonding capability and structure breaking on solvents due to -OH group. The hydrogen bonding and structure breaking capability of methanol are in the order : morphine > codeine > thebaine whereas the van der Waals interactions are probably in the reverse order. For better and useful information, extensive studies are needed.

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